

INTERCONTINENTAL LIFELONG LEARNING SKILLS**Dr. Rohini Sudhakar***Department of Lifelong Learning & Extension,
SNDT Women's University, Mumbai 20***Abstract:-**

The review of related literature shows the need for facing a “global demographic shock –a skills gap”. Due to rapid changes in the economy, changing environment and dynamic changes in society lifelong learning is needed for all which will keep all updated with the necessary knowledge and competence. Further, it is necessary to enhance the skills of less-educated citizens to make them employable and develop citizens with high levels of qualifications to create a learning society. This paper states what the National Education Policy 2020 offers to ensure that lifelong learning opportunities are provided o keep up with other nations of the world when it comes to providing lifelong learning opportunities to its people.

Keywords: *Lifelong education, lifelong learning, skills, Formal Education, Recognition, Validation and Accreditation, policy*

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Introduction

India has to achieve a massive target of learners who are outside formal system due to various reasons : As per the 2011 Census literacy of India is 74% meaning 280 million non-literates, 110 million neo literates, dropouts, out of school youth, workers, homemakers, older adults.

There are various studies and reports on lifelong learning, and it became part of the National Policy of Education 2020 discussion, particularly as global competition and economic restructuring toward knowledge-based industries became more prevalent. In order to keep up with other countries of the world UNESCO and Organization for Economic Cooperation OECD lifelong learning opportunities need to be provided to the citizens. Expanding the scope of learning from educational institutions to non -educational institutions. Learning can happen at non-educational set up-Philip Coombs-*World Education Crisis, 1976- Focus on Non-formal & Informal Education.*

Learning is a continuous process. It exists in all religions, cultures, and societies. Learning can happen anywhere and anytime and by recognizing such learning, the nations can expand the provisions for learning beyond formal education. Hence, learning can happen in a non-educational setup.

Literature review

The report of the World Economic Forum on Talent Mobility stated that the world is facing a “global demographic shock –a skills gap,” where human capital will soon rival or surpass financial capital as the critical economic engine of the future. (WEF, Executive Summary). The skill gaps vary from country to country 67% of India’s employers have reported a serious skills gap. The report suggests the “global challenge is so great that no single stakeholder can solve

it alone. Hence, there is an urgent need to ensure that all sectors like health, education, industries, commerce, and science, etc. come together to lift the barriers to talent mobility.

The Third Annual World Youth Skills Day of the UN General Assembly was marked under the theme ‘ Skill for the Future of Work’. The UN Secretary-General’s Envoy on Youth Jayathma Wickramanayake said that increasing the number of youth with relevant skills for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship will help achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In the said assembly the need for best practices and policies was stressed to address the skills gap. Considering the changing global scenario with respect to acquiring new skills and learning needs India’s National New Education Policy 2020 addresses the skills gap. By enhancing skills students of higher education would get opportunities to access quality education. As in the said policy emphasis is given on undertaking efforts to ensure that learners have flexibility in pursuing their higher education.

Further, Boston Consulting Group estimates that there will be a skilled manpower shortage of approximately **47** million by 2020 globally.

Those who are in the field of developing skills are very well aware that every individual has a tacit set of unique talents, abilities, and knowledge that hold the key to their future. And can believe that **continuous up-gradation of skills** so as to produce manpower resources of the kind and the need for the number required by the society can be met.

One of the ways of improving skills is through education. Education is intentional learning, which is acquired through the formal process. The education system runs through pre-primary education to Graduation, post-graduation, Ph.D., Postdoctoral research, etc. But, Learning may be non-intentional and is gained by an informal process.

Lifelong Education reflects a view of education as a prescriptive and normative process, while “lifelong learning” puts the emphasis on learner demand and individual choice & intrinsic motivation”. Lifelong Learning is an integration of learning and living. Learning from all domains and contexts needs to be valued.

Objective

To understand intercontinental lifelong learning efforts and to understand what the National Education Policy 2020 suggests providing lifelong learning opportunities to the citizens of India

Scope

This paper will be of help to all those in the field of academics, educational administration to enable them to provide learning opportunities to all.

Research Methodology

The descriptive research method is used for the present study. Secondary data is used to draw the findings on the subject and write the findings and conclusions based on it.

Intercontinental programs of lifelong learning

The Delors Report mentions that Lifelong Learning based on four pillars of learning:

1. **Learning to know** focuses on providing the cognitive tools required to better comprehend the world and its complexities and provide an appropriate and adequate foundation for future learning through all forms of learning- basic literacy, post-literacy, and continuing education.
2. **Learning to do** is concerned with promoting learning by doing, imparting skills that would enable individuals to effectively participate in the global economy and society.
3. **Learning to be** providing self-analytical and social skills to enable individuals to develop to their fullest potential

psycho-socially, effectively as well as physically, for the development of an all-round person. It aims at promoting a spiritual and existential broadening that bestows a final meaning in life and on the pursuit of happiness.

4. **Learning to live together:** exposes individuals to the values implicit within human rights, democratic principles, intercultural understanding and respect, and peace at all levels of society and human relationships so as to enable individuals and societies to live in peace and harmony and rediscover a meaningful relationship, and to raise the thresholds of social cohesion & integration.

Institutionalization of Lifelong Learning Programme.

There is a need to institutionalize lifelong learning as it is being done in other parts of the world:

- Examples of Lifelong Learning Institutions in Scandinavian countries- Peoples House (community Center) of Malmo, Sweden-Functions as a place of learning, entertainment, cafeteria, and networking for nonstudent youth –especially immigrants. <http://www.sofielund.org>.
- Japan : Kominkan Institutes.
- South Korea– National Institute for Lifelong Learning–Academic Credit Banks: <http://eng.nile.or.kr>.
- MALLL-European Masters Programme in Lifelong Learning. (2008-17) <http://www.lifelonglearningmasters.org>.
- Development of Lifelong Learning as a Discipline of Study: Role of University Departments of Lifelong Learning.**
- The mandate of University Departments of Lifelong Learning is to develop it as a the discipline of study and not function as mere Extension or field Departments like the Governmental and NGOs –but to take up each activity as action research the project aimed at developing innovative models, generating new knowledge, documenting and bringing out quality publications and disseminating through presentations and publications.
- Prepare professional manpower through innovative interdisciplinary courses and research programmes. www.unesco.org/education/aladin/paldin.
- Build networks with other departments within and outside university, especially those organizations actively involved in Lifelong Learning like UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning, South Korean National Institute of Lifelong Learning, European Masters Programme in Lifelong Learning. <http://www.uil.unesco.org>.

ASEM Education and Research Hub for Lifelong Learning-

An official network for university cooperation of India has to promote skill training and makes provisions for Lifelong Learning, India can have a surplus of 56 million skilled people who can meet the demand and capitalize on the demographic dividend. India has the youngest population in the world; India's median age in 2000 was less than 24 compared to 38 for Europe and 41 for Japan. As per the census of India 2011, 50% of Indians below 25 yrs, 68.4 % below 35 yrs.

Sustainable Development Goal 4 aims to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”, and carries equal importance to the other 16 goals. The New Education Policy seeks to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030. Such a lofty goal will require the entire education system to be reconfigured to support and foster learning so that all of the critical targets and goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development can be achieved (NEP; 2020). Interest in lifelong learning revived in the early 1990s, both in Europe and the United States.

Two essential components of Lifelong Learning:

1. Recognition, Validation and Accreditation (RVA) of non-formal and informal learning.
2. Skill training—economic competitiveness & life skills.

RVA-

a potential mechanism to promote continuous learning, employability, empowerment, and personal development and it is an alternative route to qualifications for adults & young people.

- Supports Lifelong Learning by recognizing a broader spectrum of learning taking place in formal, non-formal, and informal settings & building bridges among them.
- Offers opportunities to young people and adults to make the best use of their previous learning experiences. This entails granting to individuals flexible access to learning opportunities.
- an important instrument of comparison across the formal, non-formal, and informal learning sectors which are designed to eliminate discrimination against people who gain competencies from outside the formal spectrum of the education system.

Importance of Lifelong Learning for skill development.

National Mission on Skill Development (2008) observes that :

“Skills and knowledge are the driving forces of economic growth and social development for any country. Countries with higher and better levels of skills adjust more effectively to the challenges and opportunities of world of work.....Promoting lifelong learning, maintaining quality and relevance according to changing requirement particularly of the emerging knowledge economy is imperative for strengthening India’s competitiveness in the global market & support achieving rapid and inclusive growth”.

To sustain high GDP growth, it is generally agreed that much greater attention would have to be paid to the area of skill development. Further, skill development may attract investment not only from India but also from foreign countries.

The NEP has also valued Foundational Literacy and Numeracy by mentioning that it is an Urgent & Necessary Prerequisite to Learning. Emphasis needs to be paid to peoples' ability to read and write, and perform basic operations with numbers, is a necessary foundation and an indispensable prerequisite for all future schooling and lifelong learning. Further, the New Education Policy 2020 mentions that various governmental, as well as non-governmental surveys indicate that India is currently in a learning crisis: a large proportion of students currently in elementary school - estimated to be over 5 crores in number - have not attained foundational literacy and numeracy, i.e., the ability to read and comprehend basic text and the ability to carry out basic addition and subtraction with Indian numerals.

Need of Lifelong Learning for skill development

1. Low education levels in the existing workforce 63.9% of the existing workforce is either illiterate or literate up to the primary level. (38.8% illiterate & 24.9% literate up to primary)

- o High school drop out rate: Over 220 million students enrolled in Class I each year, but only 22 million of these are able to finish Class XII.
- o 90% of the students drop out at different stages before Class XII
- o 63% of the students drop out before reaching Class X.

2. Skills generated in the unorganized sector have no formal recognition & hence no career growth for workers.

3. Unemployability of the “Educated”

- The educated without professional skills constitute **69%** of the total unemployed.
- NASSCOM — the Indian IT industry's trade association — reported that **75% of the fresh engineering graduates** recruited by domestic IT providers **are unemployable**.
- Of roughly 509 million workers currently employed in India, **only 12% are skilled**.

1. *Need to focus on the skills for the informal sector*

- The largest share of new jobs in India is supposed to come from the **unorganized sector that employs up to 93% of the national workforce** and produces 60% of GDP.
- The informal sector has very low levels of productivity (incomes).
- As per the NSSO survey, a large number of workers (30%) are living below the poverty line.
- 80% of the workforce has no marketable skills. Only 2 % have skill training.

5. **Increasing demand for skilled workforce –500 million by 2022.**

Lifelong Learning as a Field of Practice: Providers of Lifelong Learning:

1. **Government Departments:** 17 Ministries: Human Resource Development, Tribal Welfare, Rural Development, Health & Family Welfare, Social Justice & Empowerment, Tourism, Industry, Food Preservation , Agriculture, Women & Child Development, Textiles, etc.
2. **Academic Institutions:** Academic Staff Colleges, University Department of Adult/Continuing/Lifelong Learning, Community Polytechnics, Community Colleges, Open Universities & National Institute of Open Learning.
3. **Nongovernmental organizations:** YMCA, Ramakrishna Mission, Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Pratham, Vivekananda Kendra, DAV & other Indian & International NGOs.
4. **Business organizations:** NIIT, APTEC, etc
5. **Professional Associations:** Medicine, Engineering, Agriculture, Adult Education etc.,.
6. **Mass media:** Television: *Gyan Darshan*; Radio: FM Channel-*Gyan Vani*.

How to operationalize Lifelong Learning programs?

1. Undertake learning need assessment of potential clientele.
2. Develop a taxonomy of local institutions and their programs.
3. Identify local expertise and employment opportunities for the learners.
4. Develop a networking strategy with different institutions and experts.
5. Work out modalities of prior learning assessment and recognition.
6. Prepare an inventory of learning resources.
7. Procure learning resources from different sources viz; open courseware. *E Gyan Kosh* of IGNOU, youtube, etc.- e.g. literacy software, SLS songs.
8. Examine and select Modular Employable Skills from the 1366 skills.

Identify research variables and plan research activities & publications.

The New Education Policy has mentioned that literacy and basic education are powerful force multipliers that greatly enhance the success of all other developmental efforts. Worldwide data on nations indicate extremely high correlations between literacy rates and per capita GDP. As per point no. 21.1 of NEP of (page no. 51-52) Adult Education and Lifelong Learning will have the following concerns:

1. The opportunity to attain foundational literacy, obtain an education, and pursue a livelihood must be viewed as basic rights of every citizen
2. Need for adopting innovative measures for Adult Education to bring out the abilities of adults
3. Volunteerism and community involvement and mobilization are key success factors of adult literacy programs, in conjunction with political will, organizational structure, proper planning, adequate financial support, and high-quality capacity building of educators and volunteers. Successful literacy programs result not only in the growth of literacy among adults but also, result in increased demand for education for all children in the community, as well as a greater community contribution to positive social change.
4. For achieving 100% literacy the policy has suggested a need for strong and innovative government initiatives for adult education - in particular, to facilitate community involvement and the smooth and beneficial integration of technology through the following manner:
5. Separate expert body of NCERT for adult education to develop a curriculum framework for adult education to develop synergy and develop an outstanding curriculum framework for literacy, numeracy, basic education, vocational skills, and beyond
6. The National Curriculum Framework for adult education will include the following 5 programs:
7. Foundational literacy and numeracy
8. Critical life skills that would include foundational literacy & numeracy, digital literacy, commercial skills, health care, and awareness, child care and education, and family welfare
9. Vocational skill development for enabling people to obtain local jobs
10. Basic education i.e. preparatory, middle, and secondary stage equivalency
11. Continuing education that would cover holistic adult education in courses like arts, science, technology, culture, sport and recreation, and advanced material on critical life skills.

Initiatives for Implementation of adult education programs:**I. Different teaching-learning material for adults and lifelong learners:**

The National Curriculum Framework of Adult Education will include different teaching-learning methods and teaching material other than that of children. Further, the adults and lifelong learners would be provided with suitable infrastructure so that all an adult will have access to adult education and lifelong learning.

II. Place and infrastructure for adult education and lifelong learning:

Schools/ school complexes & places of public library spaces can be used for organizing Adult education and lifelong learning programs. Such programs could be organized in the schools after school hours and on weekends. Hence, the infrastructure such as ICT and other equipped facilities available with the schools can be extended for community and volunteer engagement and enrichment activities.

Adult Education Centres could be housed in other Higher Education Institutions and vocational training centers.

III. Human resource for implementing National Adult Education Curriculum Framework:

The NEP demands for sharing of available human resources and facilities of the school, higher, adult and vocational education and for community and volunteer activities to ensure that National Curriculum Framework for Adult Education will be transmitted smoothly for adult education and lifelong learning. The instructors who will be required to deliver NCF for adult education will be trained by National, State, and District level resource support

institutions with the help of local NGOs and other community organizations to enhance efforts towards literacy and adult education.

IV. Participation of community members in adult education:

All-out efforts will be undertaken to seek the participation of all. Social Workers/ Counsellors would collect data of adult learners, and teachers/ tutors. Then, they will connect both the adult learners and adult education teachers to Adult Education Centers. The non-enrolled students and dropouts would be motivated to take advantage of adult education programs. Opportunities for adult education will be widely published through advertisements and announcements through events and initiatives of NGOs and other local organizations

V. Inculcating Culture of Reading through the book clubs across subjects:

NEP 2020 has emphasized that for creating reading culture there is a need for improving availability and accessibility of books with the support from Central and state governments. For this purpose all communities and educational institutions - schools, colleges, universities, mobile libraries, and public libraries, and digital libraries - will be strengthened and modernized to ensure an adequate supply of books that cater to the needs and interests of all students, including persons with disabilities and other differently-abled persons. NEP emphasized on ensuring the quality of supply of books provided to the reading rooms, rural libraries, digital/ mobile libraries.

VI. Need for leveraging technology for undertaking above initiatives: All out efforts would be required to provide for quality

NEP has mentioned the technology will be leveraged to strengthen to ensure that the above initiatives will be properly undertaken by developing required apps, online courses/ modules through satellite-based TV channels, online books, and digital libraries. Adult Education Programmes which could be online and blended will be sourced through government, philanthropic, crowdfunding.

Conclusions

- Change in nomenclature. As some people call lifelong learning adult education and some think that it is non-formal education.
- There needs to have a paradigm shift in thinking that education is not a once a lifetime activity meaning one should not stop their learning after completing Graduation or Post Graduation but, one has to keep learning throughout lifelong.
- Absence of National consultation and formulation of policy for lifelong learning in line with other countries of the world.
- Lack of clarity among academicians and administrators.
- Need to sensitize policy makers, administrators, academicians & the public.
- Absence of linkages between the two Missions of Literacy and Skill Development.
- Certification Process: Designing Prior Learning Assessment and Certification.
- setting up Accreditation Mechanism & training manpower.
- Limited support of industry to learning.
- Identifying potential areas of research, training & collaborative activities
- Leveraging technology for lifelong learning: Educating the minds of people through personal interaction, WhatsApp messages, Adult Education Tutors & Social Workers.

- Institutions will have the option to run Open Distance Learning (ODL) and online programs, provided they are accredited to do so, in order to enhance their offerings, improve access, increase GER, and provide opportunities for lifelong learning (SDG 4)
- For creating reading culture there is a need for improving availability and accessibility of books with the support from Central and state governments. For this purpose all communities and educational institutions - schools, colleges, universities, mobile libraries, and public libraries and digital libraries - will be strengthened and modernized to ensure an adequate supply of books that cater to the needs and interests of all students, including persons with disabilities and other differently-abled persons. NEP emphasized ensuring the quality of supply of books provided to the reading rooms, rural libraries, digital/ mobile libraries.
- Need for leveraging technology for undertaking above initiatives: All out efforts would be required to provide for quality learning opportunities to all.

In conclusion it can be mentioned that Lifelong learning society is a key to the twenty-first century. In order to ensure that lifelong learning opportunities would be provided to everyone, there needs to have a Lifelong Learning Policy of Nation in place to ensure that it will be strengthened. Further, there needs to have a proper mechanism to recognize learning and not just learning received through the formal mode of education but by recognizing prior learning, validating, and accrediting it.

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UNESCO BANGKOK -- Certificate course in Lifelong Learning .<https://ill-olc.net>.

(11 modules & 30 short videos)

UIL and IIEP online distance course on lifelong learning : www.iiep.unesco.org

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